

Tackling the social acceptance in deep geothermal projects: best practices and lessons learned

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ABSTRACT

Although geothermal energy is a valuable resource, the development of deep geothermal projects often encounters social resistance, which can hinder or even damage the sector nationally. Local community acceptance is crucial and influenced by factors such as low awareness of the technology, associated risks, and potential benefits. This paper draws from a review conducted within the Horizon Europe COMPASS project (www.compass-geothermal.eu), which examined case studies from 14 countries (9 in Europe) to identify strategies for improving social acceptance and avoiding the NIMBY effect.

Data sources included literature, internal project partner information, and EU-funded project reports. Key findings stress the importance of understanding the local socio-economic context and conducting preliminary studies before launching communication efforts. Effective communication must be ongoing, transparent, bidirectional, and tailored to diverse audiences. Tools like newspapers, social media, websites, and site visits can support this effort.

The study highlights that communication, community engagement, and clearly stated local benefits are essential to gaining acceptance. If any of these elements are poorly addressed, projects risk being opposed. While no universal solution exists, the research offers recommendations to support citizen involvement in decision-making and the need to adapt strategies throughout the project's duration.

1. INTRODUCTION

Geothermal energy is a sustainable and promising source to meet global energy demand, despite facing challenges, including social resistance (Bertani, 2016). Its acceptance is influenced by socio-economic, environmental, policy, governance, economic, cultural, and geographic factors.

One major reason for poor acceptance is the lack of familiarity with geothermal energy compared to other renewables, which leads to uncertainty about related technologies (Allansdóttir et al. 2019). Addressing the lack of knowledge and negative perceptions is essential.

Integrating geothermal projects with social sciences and humanities is crucial to foster dialogue with local stakeholders. Hence, viewing local communities as a barrier can worsen relationships with territories hosting plants. Technology, society and governance interact closely, as reported in Fig. 1. Social conflicts at the local level can directly or indirectly delay or stop geothermal projects (Wallquist and Holenstein 2015). Contestations can also reach national governments and the European Parliament and damage the entire sector (Pellizzone et al., 2015; Ejderyan et al., 2019).

Figure 1: Connections between society, industry and governance (Dowd et al., 2011).

As acceptance becomes increasingly important for project development, operators are striving to prevent contestations and the NIMBY (Not In My Backyard) syndrome. Appropriate and transparent communication is necessary from early stages of a project. Citizen's involvement and listening to their voices, including describing direct benefits of a geothermal project, are key solutions to improve acceptability, although approaches to be used depend on socio-economic, cultural, linguistic and geographic backgrounds.

This paper proposes research results and strategies identified within the report of the Horizon Europe COMPASS project on *Best Practices and Geothermal NIMBY Interventions* (Bonciani et al., 2023).

2. METHODOLOGY

The findings of this study are based on a systematic literature review of existing case studies and research to raise the social risk-benefit awareness and acceptance to prevent the NIMBY syndrome on deep geothermal energy projects. The work started answering research questions on what, when, who, where and why actions involving different kind of stakeholders were implemented or suggested to face the NIMBY syndrome, raise the social risk-benefit awareness and engage with the civil society.

Boundaries of the literature review were set considering the following eligibility criteria:

- a) Source of information: Scientific literature, EU project results, reports, news on sector magazines and websites of sector associations, international organizations and operators;
- b) Contexts: deep geothermal projects;
- c) Geographic coverage: more than 40 references on case studies from 9 European countries (France, Germany, Hungary, Iceland, Italy, Spain, Switzerland, Türkiye, United Kingdom) and 5 countries in other continents (Chile, New Zealand, Kenya, Japan, Philippines) with different maturity levels of their national deep geothermal markets.

Data collected were analysed to identify and assess the lessons learned and examples to be considered best practices or not to increase acceptance. Strengths and drawbacks of the actions implemented or suggested, allowed to propose tips for the planning of communication and social engagement.

3. ANALYSIS OF THE CASE STUDIES

The analysis clearly highlights that geothermal projects linked to the territory, through communication initiatives from third parties to raise awareness, and social engagement in decision-making processes, are not contested and have more likely to gain approval from local authorities. Local acceptance is achieved by highlighting community benefits, but it is crucial to clarify whether these benefits are universal to avoid unmet expectations. In addition, an assessment of local cultural and socioeconomic peculiarities is important for effective communication and engagement processes.

Besides, a distinction should be made between the public communication, which is usually conducted by independent experts, and the communication processes, which are managed by private companies (Allansdottir et al. 2019). Both kinds of communications complete each other and are important to allow the public to have all the information they need, to have an opinion on the project and take decisions.

Chapters below report relevant examples on how local communities were engaged and how geothermal projects and linked benefits were communicated to local communities.

3.1 Communicating and engaging with local communities

Open and transparent communication of the risks associated with the use of deep geothermal resources allowed the geothermal project in St. Gallen (Switzerland) to be resumed after a seismic event of magnitude 3,5 during drilling operations, thanks to the broad public support. Indeed, when the risks of the project are communicated before the event, there is always emphasis on the measures in place to deal with them (Eyderyan et al., 2019).

Likewise, the strategy adopted for geothermal projects in Trebur and Groß-Gerau (Germany), around 30 km SW from Frankfurt, allowed their development in a friendly and supportive public environment. This highlights the importance of communication and public engagement for more robust decisions on if, where and how geothermal power should be deployed. Wallquist and Hostenstein (2015) reported that the successful public engagement process included a preliminary study on local stakeholders and their views on geothermal energy, followed by project information sharing, during public meetings and discussions. Afterwards, an advisory board with local stakeholders representing environmental protection groups, farmers, public institutions and individuals, discussed on geothermal energy in its aspects and consequences. Outcomes from these discussions were summarised to report conditions required to accept the project. Other successful example in the Upper Rhine area (Germany) was described by Douwe et al. (2016). The geothermal operator engaged with local communities during specific events and reported clear information on geothermal energy and its projects through the website. It set up a communication centre, promoted educational initiatives and gave opportunity to visit drilling sites. This proves the importance of citizens' direct involvement in different plant construction phases, to also alleviate concerns related to an underground energy source, unfamiliar for the most, as out of sight and out of mind (Stewart and Lewis, 2017; Kluge and Ziefle, 2016).

The United Down Deep Geothermal Project (United Kingdom) implemented a successful community engagement plan. Key actions included researching local concerns, attending events, direct communication, and educational outreach. Trust-building and regular interactions allowed the operator to understand and address issues effectively and virtual meetings ensured continued dialogue during the pandemic. Youth and older adults showed higher engagement, helping spread awareness and support for renewable energy initiatives (Farndale and Law, 2022).

However, prompt communication is not always effective in tackling local oppositions. Ejderyan et al.

(2019; 2020) reported that the operator informed the public just after the plant site selection and a committee of local politicians, representatives of local companies and NGOs was chosen to act as an intermediary between the local communities and the developers in the rural town of Haute-Sorne (Switzerland). The committee informed developers about public concerns and organized newsletter and public events to update the population on the project progress. Nonetheless, the project was delayed due to the dissent of a local group, which claimed concerns about noise risk and negative impacts on the landscape and water resources. The same group collected signatures to vote for the ban of geothermal projects in the Canton of Jura.

A monodirectional communication can create public skepticism, as was the case of a public assembly held by a municipality in Monte Amiata (Italy) for a binary plant. Despite efforts of the company to clearly provide information on geothermal energy, the project and its risks, as well as the results of a Life Cycle Assessment, and the collaboration with the municipality, the public could only ask questions about the project at the end of the assembly and no sessions were held to engage and promote the direct participation of citizens in the decision-making process (Bonciani et al., 2023).

The implementation of ineffective communication without social engagement may lead to local contestations. A geothermal project was stopped after a 3,4-magnitude earthquake in Basel (Switzerland), due to the injection of high pressurised water for the hydraulic stimulation of the geothermal reservoir. Controversies about the absence of communication, the lack of a risk assessment and the quality of the project itself generated contestations by local communities and authorities (Eyderyan et al. 2020).

Manzella et al. (2018) reported that the fragmentation of information, uncertainty and doubts about the reliability of sources of data is a common problem, in Italy as elsewhere. One of the reasons of geothermal projects oppositions from small groups in Italy may be linked to concerns on environmental risks. Results of surveys conducted in areas far from geothermal installations (Palermo) and closer to these plants (Viterbo) reported concerns on a possible geothermal development in this latter area. All participants requested more information and communication on geothermal (Reith et al., 2013; Pellizzone et al., 2019) and they did not feel sufficiently informed to have voice in decision making (Manzella et al., 2018).

In many considered cases for this research, the communication involved or was proposed by the local authorities, as these pursue the public interest and operate in the general interest. In Haute-Sorne, some residents would even have preferred discussions at municipal council sessions to influence more decisions, instead of the information meetings held by the project promoters with governmental officials, which they reported it did not provide legitimacy (Ejderyan et al., 2019). Nonetheless, distrust in policy makers (considered not impartial) is a key limiting factor for

geothermal development support in Italy (Manzella et al., 2018) and in some cases the local communities would prefer the involvement of local scientists (Pellizzone et al., 2019). Differences between these examples demonstrate that each case is different and the initial awareness on geothermal technologies, as well as the local cultural and socio-economic conditions, must be carefully studied before planning communication and engagement.

Although all the considered studies agree on the need to start involving all the local stakeholders, authorities and citizens from the early exploration stages of a geothermal project, there are no standard procedures for participation (Vargas-Payera, 2020).

3.2 Proposing local benefits

Local acceptance is also gained through highlighting the benefits or improvement of the community's living conditions.

St. Gallen and Geneva in Switzerland showed that the direct use of geothermal heat can play an important role in making deep geothermal locally acceptable (Ejderyan et al., 2020). In the first case, promoters emphasized the potential for local use of the heat generated, while the geothermal development program in Geneva gave more importance to heat production than electricity generation.

It is generally more challenging to foster local support for projects that only entail electricity generation, since the local population may have the impression to bear the risks without direct benefits. Nonetheless, the Theistareykir geothermal power plant (Bjarnadóttir and Knútsson, 2021) provided electrical stability and increased power availability in Northeast Iceland, opening up new industrial opportunities. These benefits to the community and the timely project development created a high level of satisfaction among the local communities.

Geothermal projects in the region around the city of Strasbourg (France) were contested by residents' associations and municipalities (Chavot et al., 2018). Reasons for these oppositions were related to concerns on the seismic and explosion risks, the reliability of the operator, which had poor experience in geothermal energy, the lack of compensation for territories and project's failures to consider environmental and urban planning constraints. In addition, the lack of coherence of the projects and the choice of the plants location, compared to local development plans, the aquifer and the distance from existing district heating networks, were contested. Acceptance was facilitated for other projects in the same area, thanks to upstream discussions and partnerships between the operator and the municipal government that reinforced the coherence of the project with local policies.

However, in a hypothetical construction of a geothermal plant, it is key to clearly indicate whether the social benefits will be universal for the entire population or not (CEGA, 2022). Offering benefits can

lead to expectations, which is a double-edged sword if these are high and cannot be fulfilled, as it was in the case of Tolhuaca in Chile (Martinez-Reyes, 2020). Here, part of the public engagement strategy consisted in offering direct benefits to the communities near the Tolhuaca site. This included jobs, access roads and 1% of the production revenues. The distant residents' associations thought that they would have access to cheaper energy and more job opportunities when the project started. However, these expectations were not met as the project evolved and stakeholders found that they would not get cheaper electricity, and that the jobs would not be suitable for the local population. The unmet high expectations did not create a positive perception and generated distrust towards the company. Indeed, when energy poverty is high and the lack of equitable access to high-quality energy services may

lead to high expectations (CEGA, 2022), which should be effectively managed to avoid discontent.

Furthermore, benefits and communication without social engagement may lead to oppositions. For example, Torsello et al. (2019) reported that despite in some cases agreements between the operator and authorities resulted in advantages for local communities and a long-lasting communication on geothermal, small groups of citizens are still opposing operating and future projects in Italy.

As a result of the analysis on different experiences considered in this research, Table 1 summarises lessons learned from communication and engagement strategies to address the social acceptance in geothermal projects.

Table 1: Positive and negative examples of strategies to raise social acceptance on geothermal projects.

	Positive examples	Negative examples
Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Communication starts from the early stages of the project development · Communication tailored to different kinds of stakeholders and local conditions · Communication of risks and mitigation measures · Involve local authorities and scientists. · Clearly explain benefits · Explain benefits from direct uses of heat 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Top-down communication · Communication only from operators · Partial or incorrect communication · Creation of high expectations · Communicate benefits only
Social engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Citizen involvement in decision making processes · Involvement of different kinds of local stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Plan the actions without involving local actors and authorities · Top-down approach · “Closed doors” initiatives, without involving local communities

3.3 The Social License to Operate, a model to understand the interaction between communities and projects

One emerging approach to address public acceptance in geothermal energy development—particularly in high-enthalpy or superhot contexts—is the Social License to Operate (SLO) framework (Barich et al., 2022). SLO goes beyond formal permitting processes, providing a structured lens to assess and monitor trust, procedural justice, risk perception, and community identity throughout the lifecycle of geothermal projects (Barich et al., 2022, Fernandez et al., 2022). In Hungary, for example, a recent empirical study conducted in the city of Szeged—home to one of Europe’s largest geothermal district heating systems—demonstrated that public support was closely tied to perceived benefits, procedural fairness, and social cohesion (Hildebrand et al., 2022). The Hungarian case illustrates that, even in large-scale infrastructure projects with considerable local impact, high levels of public acceptance can be achieved when transparent

communication, community engagement, and trust-building are prioritized. In the COMPASS project, such findings are being taken into account to design communication and stakeholder engagement strategies for superhot geothermal wells, where social acceptance is particularly critical given the technical risks, permitting hurdles, and perceived uncertainties often associated with ultra-deep and high-temperature drilling.

4. RECOMMENDATIONS TO ADDRESS THE NIMBY SYNDROME IN GEOTHERMAL PROJECTS

This paragraph attempts to provide recommendations to develop a process of raising acceptance towards deep geothermal energy projects, grounding on case studies described and discussed in the previous chapters. Operators and public authorities are the target of these suggestions, which are reported in Fig. 2 and start from the initial stages of the project development.

Figure 2: Main tips to increase acceptance of geothermal projects, from their early development stages.

The communication and engagement strategy should be adapted over time.

The communication and engagement of local communities and authorities are critical factors for the success of a project and operators and developers should dedicate part of the project budget to these activities.

5. CONCLUSIONS

There is a wide range of factors influencing the perception of deep geothermal energy projects, including local cultural, social and socioeconomical specificities. There are no standard procedures to address these challenges and a study of local peculiarities is essential, before implementing effective actions to prevent contestations and ensure acceptance. Furthermore, the perception of the same project can change over time and strategies to address acceptance should be adapted accordingly.

Proper and transparent communication on a geothermal project and its technology, so as the engagement of local communities in decision-making processes are key actions for an effective plan addressing acceptance of local communities. The third key measure to consider is proposing and communicating direct socioeconomic benefits for the territory to compensate for the use of a local resource. This could include the creation of new jobs, financial resources for local authorities and direct use of waste heat: a source of affordable and sustainable heating and cooling for both buildings and production processes.

If one of these three elements is not considered and treated appropriately, there is a risk of losing trust and the likelihood of protests emerging is enormously higher.

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